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Understanding Audio Source Separation in Carnatic Music with Multimodal Data

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Abstract

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the internal mechanisms of audio-visual source separation models, focusing on how performer motion guides source separation in Carnatic music. To move beyond "black box" performance metrics, we employ a dual approach combining model-independent analysis of audio-visual synchrony with model-specific interpretability techniques applied to Voice-Vision Transformer (VoViT) architectures. A cross-correlation and sliding-window analysis on the Saraga dataset first establishes instrument-specific temporal patterns, revealing that targeted instrument-specific motion features exhibit stronger and more consistent correlations with audio dynamics than general body motion. While global linear audio-visual synchrony is weak, these analyses highlight the importance of localised and instrument-specific motion cues. Subsequently, we apply gradient-based saliency methods to a vocal separation model, demonstrating its primary reliance on facial keypoints. Ablation studies causally confirm that these facial regions are crucial for vocal separation, while body motion contributes minimally. We further analyze the attention mechanisms of a vocal & violin model to understand how it disentangles spectrally overlapping sources, specifically through a revised hybrid fusion architecture. FiLM (Feature-wise Linear Modulation) analysis reveals that visual information causally modulates audio features by consistently amplifying or suppressing them, acting as a dynamic gating mechanism. This research provides a framework for interpreting gesture-based audio-visual systems, offers novel insights into audio-visual learning, and contributes to the development of more transparent and culturally-aware Music Information Retrieval technologies. Code available at: <https://github.com/theofuhrmann/masters-thesis>

Keywords: Model Interpretability; Audio-visual; Source Separation; Carnatic Music;

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Isolating a single sound source from a complex auditory scene, known as audio source separation, is a key task with applications ranging from hearing aids and speech recognition to music production and remixing. Early approaches were based on statistical signal processing, but the rise of deep learning has brought major advances, enabling models to separate complex musical mixtures with impressive accuracy.

In parallel to advances in audio-only methods, researchers have explored multimodal approaches that incorporate visual cues (such as lip movements or musical gestures) to help disambiguate sound. These audio-visual models complement audio-only systems and have opened new possibilities for improving separation. However, their growing complexity often comes at the cost of interpretability. As these deep learning models become harder to analyze, it becomes increasingly difficult to understand how they make decisions. This opacity limits our ability to trust, debug, and improve them, and makes it harder to see possible connections between sight and sound.

This thesis tackles the challenge by shifting the focus from performance metrics to model interpretability. We explore how state-of-the-art audio-visual systems use visual information to separate sound sources. To ground our analysis, we focus on Carnatic music, a classical tradition from Southern India known for its rich acoustic textures and complex performance practices. Its unique gestures and expressive style

provide a compelling and underexplored setting for developing and testing methods that reveal how these models actually work.

1.1 Motivation

This work is motivated by three key goals related to interpretability, methodology, and cultural scope in audio-visual learning and music information retrieval (MIR).

First, as audio-visual source separation models grow more complex, they often become difficult to interpret. These systems may achieve strong performance, but it's not always clear how or why they work. Understanding which visual features a model uses (whether it's lip movements, head gestures, or arm motions) is essential for building more transparent, robust, and efficient systems.

Second, most interpretability research in vision focuses on pixel-based inputs like images or videos. In contrast, this work applies interpretability techniques to structured visual data: the 2D coordinates of body and facial keypoints. This shift allows for more targeted and quantifiable insights into how specific gestures affect the separation process.

Third, this research aims to broaden the cultural focus of MIR. By studying Carnatic music and using the Saraga audiovisual dataset, we explore a musical tradition that is rich, complex, and underrepresented in MIR research. Carnatic performances pose unique challenges that push existing models beyond their typical Western contexts. This work contributes to building more inclusive and generalizable music technologies.

1.2 Objectives

The primary goal of this thesis is to investigate and interpret the role of performer motion in guiding audio-visual source separation models within the context of Carnatic music. To achieve this, we pursue the following specific objectives:

1. **To conduct a model-independent analysis of the temporal relation-**

ship between performer motion and audio features. Before examining any specific model, we first establish a baseline understanding of the inherent audio-visual correlations in Carnatic music. We use cross-correlation techniques to quantify synchrony and estimate temporal lags between gestures and sound across different instruments.

2. **To apply gradient-based interpretability methods and ablation studies to a state-of-the-art vocal separation model.** We analyze an adapted VoViT architecture to identify which facial and body keypoints are most influential for isolating the vocalist's track. This involves implementing and comparing several attribution methods to produce robust and meaningful explanations.
3. **To analyze the attention mechanisms of a VoViT variation for vocal and violin separation.** We study an adapted VoViT architecture that separates vocals and violin using distinct models and an attention + FiLM fusion module. By examining the attention and FiLM behavior in the fusion layer, we aim to understand how the system balances and integrates audio and visual features to separate these two overlapping sources.

Chapter 2

State Of The Art

This chapter reviews recent advances in audio source separation and audio–visual source separation with an emphasis on multimodal strategies. We first discuss audio–only separation methods, followed by a review of approaches that leverage visual cues. Then we present key datasets for evaluating these methods, and finally we focus on the state of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) in Carnatic music.

2.1 Source Separation

2.1.1 Audio Source Separation

Audio source separation, often referred to as the “cocktail party problem”, a term coined by Cherry [1] to describe the human ability to focus on a single conversation in a noisy environment, is the task of extracting individual source signals from a mixed audio recording. Traditional approaches in this field have relied on statistical and matrix–factorization techniques such as Non–negative Matrix Factorization (NMF), which decomposes the magnitude spectrogram of a mixture into a set of basis functions and their corresponding activations. In 1999, Lee and Seung [2] demonstrated that NMF could learn interpretable parts–based representations. Consequently, later studies [3] applied NMF to the magnitude spectrogram of instrument performances with notes exhibiting a static harmonic profile. This decomposition resulted in two

matrices: W , capturing the spectral characteristics of the notes, and H , representing their temporal activity, enabling effective source separation.

Lately, deep-learning methods have pushed audio source separation to new heights by effectively handling the inherent non-linear behavior of audio signals, allowing these models to tackle complex, real-world scenarios. U-Net based architectures, originally designed for biomedical image segmentation by Ronneberger et al. [4], have become a cornerstone of source separation research. U-Net features an encoder-decoder structure with skip connections, which facilitate the reconstruction of fine-grained details by retaining essential features across different resolution levels. A pioneering example is the work by Jansson et al. [5], who fed magnitude spectrograms to a U-Net convolutional network for singing voice separation, marking a significant milestone in the field. Following this, the Wave-U-Net architecture [6] adapted the traditional U-Net for end-to-end audio source separation in the one-dimensional time domain, further enhancing performance. Deezer’s Spleeter leveraged a similar approach, providing a user-friendly tool that has gained widespread adoption [7]. More recently, Demucs [8] adapted Conv-TasNet [9], a fully convolutional time-domain audio separation network originally designed for low-latency speech separation, and incorporated two BLSTM layers. Its hybrid version further improved separation quality by adding a spectrogram branch [10]. Other architectural paradigms have also been explored. Deep Clustering [11] separates sources by clustering them in class-conditional embeddings, while Open-Unmix [12] consists of a set of fully open-source, single-target models based on three-layer bidirectional deep LSTMs.

Beyond specific architectures, large-scale initiatives have further advanced the field. The Music Demixing Challenge [10], a competition where participants submit audio source separation models evaluated on a secret test set, led to the development of the hybrid Demucs. More recent advances include Few-Shot Musical Source Separation [13], which facilitates generalization by conditioning the network on a few audio examples of the target instrument using feature-wise linear modulation (FiLM), and SCNet [14], which applies sparse compression on subbands of the spectrogram to

focus on the most informative frequencies. Together, these developments highlight the ongoing effort to achieve more efficient and higher-quality separation.

2.1.2 Audio-Visual Source Separation

Audio-visual approaches exploit the complementary information available in the visual domain to improve separation quality. This paradigm was first explored by Sodoeyer et al. [15] in 2002, who developed a statistical model combining lip shape parameters with spectral characteristics for speech separation.

As with audio-only separation, deep-learning methods have revolutionized audio-visual source separation by learning complex multimodal patterns. These approaches use different visual cues to guide separation. Lip movements, for instance, have been widely used: Lu et al. [16] trained a two-branch convolutional neural network (CNN) model on grayscale video and optical flow data of lip regions to improve speech separation. Objects, such as instruments, have also been extensively used. The Sound of Pixels [17] used a self-supervised mix-and-separate training pipeline, which artificially mixes audio from different videos, and extracted visual features from each video pixel to locate the regions corresponding to different audio sources. This framework was later refined by Gao et al. [18], who incorporated a co-separation training objective that uses unlabeled detected object similarity to associate sounds, and by Zhu et al. [19], who performed multi-stage refinement. Beyond faces and objects, full-body motion and gestures have also been explored. Gan et al. [20] fused video and graph representations of body landmarks at the network bottleneck.

More recent methods have introduced a semantic dimension into the separation process. Query-based models use high-level visual features as queries to specify which audio source to isolate. Tan et al. [21] proposed a self-supervised approach that uses natural language queries to separate audio, and Chen et al. [22] used a flexible query expansion mechanism to generalize to new instruments without having to fine-tune the entire network.

Another strategy involves graph-based modeling, which builds explicit represen-

tations of the visual scene, encoding spatial and semantic relationships between objects. For instance, the AVSGS approach [23] constructs scene graphs whose segmented subgraphs are associated with unique sounds. Montesinos et al. [24] refined the approach of Gan et al. [20] by focusing specifically on face landmarks instead of full-body motion. Expanding on these methods, the VoViT architecture [25] forgoes raw video input and instead concatenates body landmark graphs with spectrogram vectors as input to a transformer, replacing the UNet used by Gan et al. Additionally, VoViT predicts a complex spectrogram rather than relying on the mixture’s phase, effectively reducing the robotic artifacts often present in separated voices.

2.2 Interpretability and Model Analysis

While the majority of research in audio source separation has focused on architectural innovation and performance improvement, a parallel and increasingly relevant area is understanding how these models make decisions. Interpretability research aims to examine the internal mechanisms of these models and identify which features contribute most to specific outputs.

Several methods have been developed to visualize and interpret the internal workings of deep networks. Erhan et al. [26] used activation maximization to reveal higher-layer features, while Zeiler and Fergus [27] introduced deconvolutional techniques to diagnose the role of intermediate convolutional layers. Baehrens et al. [28] proposed a model-agnostic method to explain individual classification decisions by highlighting influential input dimensions. Saliency mapping [29] extended this idea by identifying input regions most relevant to a model’s output, setting the stage for Grad-CAM [30], which is widely used to visualize spatial contributions in CNNs. In audio-visual learning, similar ideas are applied to localize relevant visual features. For example, The Sound of Pixels [17] generates sound energy heatmaps over video frames, offering direct insight into how spatial cues guide source separation.

Another widely used technique is ablation studies, which involve systematically removing or disabling components of a model to assess their impact on performance.

For instance, Meyes et al. [31] evaluated the contribution of different neural layers by systematically removing specific units and observing the resulting performance changes on the MNIST dataset.

In this work, we apply gradient-based saliency methods to structured visual inputs (2D facial and body landmark coordinates) to identify which landmarks most influence the model’s voice separation output. Unlike typical saliency methods applied to raw images, this approach provides direct insight into how motion and pose guide the model’s predictions, offering a novel perspective on the role of visual cues in audio-visual source separation.

2.3 Datasets

Music Information Research (MIR) has traditionally focused on Western music, often underrepresenting the diverse range of musical traditions worldwide. This imbalance has motivated recent efforts to incorporate non-Western music styles into MIR studies. As highlighted by Serra [32], adopting a multicultural approach is crucial to developing more inclusive and representative computational methodologies.

Notable Western-focused datasets used for multimodal audio source separation include AudioSet [33], a large collection of 10-second YouTube videos manually labeled among 632 audio classes; MUSIC [17], which provides 714 labeled YouTube recordings of musical performances; and URMP [34], a high-quality manually recorded audiovisual dataset of multi-instrument classical music pieces.

Building on recent efforts to expand MIR research beyond Western music, we use the Saraga Audiovisual dataset [35], a recently developed large-scale multimodal collection designed for the study of Carnatic music. Built on the principles of the original Saraga dataset [36], which included only audio recordings, this dataset contains 42 recorded Carnatic concerts, totaling over 60 hours of audio-visual data, with multi-track audio recordings and synchronized video footage.

Additionally, the Sanidha dataset serves as another valuable audio-visual resource for Carnatic music research [37]. It contains 5 high-definition recordings of Carnatic

concerts, totaling 15.35 hours. Each performer was recorded separately, with simultaneous video recordings conducted in different rooms to ensure clean, isolated audio and synchronized visual data. These datasets support ongoing efforts to diversify MIR and advance methods for non-Western music.

2.4 Carnatic Music in MIR

Despite the dominance of Western music in MIR, there has been a growing recognition of the need to study non-Western musical traditions. Carnatic music, with its unique raga-based structure, intricate ornamentation, and complex rhythmic patterns, presents both significant challenges and exciting opportunities for MIR.

Early studies explored Carnatic music through different MIR techniques. For example, research on singer identification in Carnatic music [38] leveraged the 22-tone octave system to develop cepstral coefficients for capturing distinct vocal characteristics. Later, a study on computational approaches for understanding melody in Carnatic music [39] emphasized the need for tailored methodologies in music information processing for Carnatic music. Another example is a study on raga classification [40], which proposed a new system to classify music into ragas using different audio features.

More recently, advances in source separation have addressed challenges in Carnatic singing. Plaja-Roglans et al. [41] trained a cold diffusion model to mitigate audio bleeding in performance recordings. In another study, they developed a system to generate vocal pitch annotations using the Saraga dataset, creating the Saraga-Carnatic-Melody-Synth (SCMS) dataset, which was then used to train a state-of-the-art pitch extraction model for Carnatic music [42].

Building on this, Shankar et al. [43] leveraged the Saraga audio-visual dataset to adapt the VoViT architecture for gesture-guided source separation in Carnatic concert recordings. They explored different audiovisual fusion strategies and showed that integrating facial and body keypoints improves vocal and violin separation, even in the presence of source bleeding and partial visual occlusion.

Chapter 3

Dataset and Preprocessing

3.1 Dataset Overview

We focused on performances with a consistent left-to-right layout (mridangam, vocal, and violin) as this setup provides a more controlled environment for multimodal analysis. In this configuration, side artists typically face inward toward the vocalist, causing one side of their body to be partially or fully occluded. This asymmetry in visibility can affect the reliability of pose estimation, so we limited our selection to concerts with a consistent layout to ensure that the same side of the mridangam and violin players remained visible throughout. For this reason, we used only 26 concert recordings from the Saraga Audiovisual collection, totaling around 28 hours of audio-visual material.

A minority of performances followed an alternate layout (violin, vocal, and mridangam), which were excluded to ensure pose estimation consistency. However, due to improved bow visibility, these 3 recordings are revisited in Chapter 4 for a violin-specific case study involving more specialized motion features. Although limited to 3 concerts, this violin subset provides nearly 4 hours of music, offering sufficient within-performance variability to analyze audiovisual correlations, while generalization to other performers remains a caveat.

3.2 Pose Estimation and Instrument Labeling

Pose estimation was performed using the RTMW-X (384x288) model from MMPose, following the setup by Rodrigues [44]. Since performers remain seated in fixed positions throughout each concert, mean centroids were computed across the full duration of each performance. Detections with low temporal presence were discarded as likely false positives, such as standing spectators. To filter the remaining false positives, mainly wall artwork depicting human figures, the estimations above a certain vertical threshold were excluded. Each valid estimation was then assigned to one of the three instruments based on a manually generated left-to-right performer layout annotated for each video. The assignments were verified by visualizing short clips with color-coded skeleton overlays, one color per instrument, confirming both spatial consistency and pose estimation quality (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Color-coded pose estimation visualization.

3.3 Feature Extraction

3.3.1 Motion

Keypoints were normalized per performer by centering and rescaling around their spatio-temporal mean to ensure consistent scale and position. Lower body keypoints were discarded due to limited movement (as performers remain seated) and inaccurate pose estimation from clothing and instrument occlusions. For the vocalist, both arms were used; for side instrumentalists (mridangam and violin), only the visible arm was retained due to frequent occlusions.

For the initial analysis, speed and acceleration were computed using NumPy’s **gradient** function over the 2D keypoints extracted using MMPose, and averaged over the full upper body as well as specific regions: left arm, right arm, head, face, left hand, and right hand.

In addition to these general motion descriptors, two case studies were conducted focusing on more domain-specific movement cues:

Vocal-specific features: To capture gestures directly related to vocal production [15, 45], we focused on mouth and jaw motion. We extracted 3D face keypoints using the 3DDFA face pose estimator, which is used in the *vovit-fb* model analysed in Chapter 5. The 3D nature of the keypoints allowed us to rotate the face to a frontal position, minimizing the influence of head pose on the measurements.

During inspection, we found that 3DDFA’s face tracking sometimes failed when the vocalist’s face was occluded or turned away, producing inaccurate landmarks. To address this, we used the more stable MMPose nose keypoint as a reference, discarding frames where its distance from the 3DDFA face centroid exceeded a set threshold. This reduced noise in the vocal-specific features.

From the filtered and aligned keypoints, we computed two features to capture facial movements. The first is **mouth area**, which combines mouth width and height to approximate the degree of mouth opening. The second is **nose-to-jaw distance**, which tracks the vertical displacement of the jaw.

Violin-specific features: For violinists with non-occluded bowing arms, we computed additional motion descriptors using the 2D keypoints from MMPose to capture bowing gestures more directly. We chose these features based on their clear relevance in prior biomechanical studies [46, 47]. The first, **wrist velocity**, captures the speed of the bowing motion. The second, **elbow angle**, is defined by the angle between the shoulder, elbow, and wrist, reflecting articulation changes during bow strokes. Finally, **arm extension** measures the Euclidean distance between the shoulder and wrist, indicating the degree of arm reach during performance.

3.3.2 Audio

Audio features include onset envelope and Root-Mean-Square (RMS) energy, both extracted using Librosa. The onset envelope highlights sudden changes in energy, often corresponding to note or syllable attacks, while RMS energy provides a measure of overall loudness over time. Prior work has shown that these temporal energy variations are closely coupled with articulatory motion in audiovisual speech [45]. For the mridangam, stereo tracks were mixed into a single mono signal before calculating the features.

3.4 Synchronization and Source Alignment

To enable multimodal frame-wise analysis, audio and video data were temporally aligned. Although most Saraga videos were recorded at 30 frames per second (fps), some performances had slightly different frame rates. Videos recorded at 29.99 fps were resampled to exactly 30 fps for consistency. Videos recorded at 24 fps were left unchanged to preserve their original temporal resolution. Each song's fps was stored in the metadata. Pose estimation was performed at the original (or adjusted) video fps, and motion features were computed accordingly. To enable a frame-wise audiovisual correlation analysis, the 48 kHz audio was resampled using linear interpolation to match the number of video frames.

The video data was recorded concurrently with the performance, while the audio was captured separately in four different tracks (one per instrument, with the mridangam using two tracks). Although these sources originate from the same performance, they were pieced together manually, which could cause a potential desynchronization due to the editing, recording or post-processing artifacts. While no obvious desynchronization was perceived during qualitative inspection, potential misalignment is formally assessed in Chapter 4.

3.4.1 Data Filtering

Pose estimation confidence varied across instruments and frames. In total, 0.79% of frames contained NaN values, and 5.5% had low confidence scores¹. Mean confidence scores per instrument were as follows: mridangam: 7.16, violin: 7.11, vocal: 8.00. This distribution is expected, as vocalists typically face the camera directly and are subject to less occlusion. Frames with confidence below the confidence threshold were discarded, and these missing or unreliable values were masked in all subsequent analyses. No interpolation or padding was applied given the relatively small amount of unreliable data. As a result, all subsequent analyses were conducted only on high-confidence, temporally aligned frames².

3.5 Limitations

Despite the care taken during preprocessing and annotation, several limitations affect the dataset, which are considered when interpreting motion–audio relationships in the subsequent chapters:

- **Occlusions:** The vocalist is sometimes partially occluded by the microphone, and the lateral positioning of the violinist and mridangam player leads to frequent self-occlusion or loss of hand detail.
- **Pose Estimation Detail:** The resolution of the original recordings limits the fine-grained accuracy of pose estimations, particularly for fast hand movements or finger articulation.
- **Audio Bleed:** Although the audio was recorded in isolated tracks, all instruments were captured in the same physical space, leading to audio bleeding across tracks. This may reduce the precision of instrument-specific audio features and complicate their correlation with motion data.

¹The confidence threshold was set to 3, with scores ranging up to ≈ 11

²Some instruments, such as the mridangam, naturally exhibit a delay between physical motion and corresponding audio due to the physics of sound production and human performance. No corrective temporal alignment was applied to account for these expressive lags. Their impact is analyzed later in Chapter 4 in the context of audiovisual correlations.

Chapter 4

Correlation and Timing Analysis

This chapter explores the temporal relationships between motion and audio features across different instruments. We analyze how facial and body movements correlate with sonic events over time and discuss the implications of observed lags or synchrony between modalities.

4.1 Sliding Window Correlation Analysis

4.1.1 Speed and Acceleration

To capture local temporal dependencies between modalities, we apply a sliding window correlation approach between motion and audio features. Pearson correlations are computed over a 0.5-second window with a 0.1-second step size. To focus on meaningful interactions, only correlations with an absolute value above 0.5 are retained¹. Strong correlation windows are identified across four feature pairs: motion speed vs. audio onset, motion speed vs. audio RMS, motion acceleration vs. audio onset, and motion acceleration vs. audio RMS. The number of high-correlation windows is then aggregated per body part and per instrument to highlight which regions contribute most consistently to the audio signal across all feature pairs.

¹Both strong positive and strong negative correlations between audio and motion features are treated as equally meaningful, as they each reflect consistent relationships.

A large portion of the dataset exhibits strong correlations between motion and audio features. Overall, 95.5% of the total duration contains at least one strongly correlated window. By instrument, coverage is 60.8% for mridangam, 76.7% for vocals, and 60.9% for violin. To account for temporal overlap, we also computed coverage using non-overlapping windows (0.5 s hop), finding 64.6% overall, with 26.3% for mridangam, 37.9% for vocals, and 25.6% for violin. These results suggest that a notable fraction of the dataset may exhibit audio-motion coupling, with the effect persisting even when accounting for window overlap, providing a model-independent perspective before introducing audio-visual source separation analyses.

Figure 2: Number of strong windows per body part and instrument.

In Figure 2, the vocalist shows the highest number of strong correlations, likely due to longer active performance durations and frontal visibility, which improve key-point estimation. For the instrumentalists, correlations are slightly higher in the arms/hands than in the face or head, consistent with their role in sound production. The vocalist also shows more hand than face correlations, possibly reflecting expressive gestures. The mridangam performer shows fewer correlations overall, as only the non-occluded arm was visible, representing half of the instrument’s activity. More generally, the relatively uniform counts across body parts, especially for side-facing performers, suggest that occlusions and pose estimation errors dilute motion signals in active regions like the hands, while more consistently estimated areas such as the face contain stable but less informative correlations. These aggregate results should therefore be interpreted with caution given the limitations noted in Section 3.5.

4.1.2 Vocal-Specific Features

We applied the sliding-window correlation method to two vocal-specific facial features (mouth area and nose-to-jaw distance) extracted from the 3D face keypoints. To ensure reliability, only frames where the 3DDFA face estimation passed the accuracy check described in Section 3.3.1 were included.

Case study. To better illustrate the analysis, we examined a short performance segment from *Ameya Karthikeyan - Jalajakshi* and plotted the temporal evolution of correlations between the two vocal-specific motion features (mouth area and nose-to-jaw distance) and the audio features (RMS energy and onset envelope). Only the first 30 seconds of the 41-second performance were retained after filtering unreliable 3DDFA frames. As shown in Figure 3, both audio features follow a broadly similar temporal trend, although RMS energy consistently reaches higher correlation values than the onset envelope.

Figure 3: Temporal evolution of vocal motion features vs audio features correlation throughout the performance of *Ameya Karthikeyan - Jalajakshi*

Both vocal-specific features produced comparable counts of strong correlation windows: 48 for the onset envelope and 209 for RMS energy (combined over the two

motion features). For comparison, general motion features (mean speed and mean acceleration) produced 84 strong windows for the onset envelope and 153 for RMS energy.

Dataset-wide results. Extending the analysis to the full dataset provided stronger evidence that vocal-specific features consistently capture vocal dynamics more effectively than general motion descriptors. Across all performances, the proportion of strong correlation windows was higher for facial features for both audio measures. For RMS energy, vocal-specific features reached 35.96% of frames in strong correlation, compared to 21.32% for general motion features. For the onset envelope, the difference was smaller but still favoured vocal-specific features (10.08% vs. 9.01%). When combining both audio features, vocal-specific features achieved 23.02% strong windows versus 15.16% for general motion features.

Interpretation. Both the case study and the aggregated analysis indicate that targeted facial features capture temporal variations in vocal production more effectively than general body motion descriptors. This is particularly evident in their stronger coupling with RMS energy, suggesting that mouth and jaw movements provide a more direct and consistent visual correlate of vocal loudness across the dataset. These results indicate that the advantage of targeted facial motion features is not limited to individual performances but is robust across the entire dataset.

4.1.3 Violin-Specific Features

We applied the same sliding window correlation analysis used for the vocal-specific features to three violin-specific motion descriptors (wrist velocity, elbow angle, and arm extension, described in Section 3.3.1) across all performances in which the violinist’s bowing arm was clearly visible. Due to the scarcity of violinists exposing their bowing hand, this dataset-wide analysis only includes 15 performances from 3 different artists.

Case study. We illustrate the analysis on a full 2-minute 42-second performance, *Bhargavi Chandrasekar – Challare Rmachandru*, in which the violinist performs

during the majority of the time. However, for readability purposes, we only plot the analysis on a 30s segment.

Figure 4: Temporal evolution of violin motion features vs audio features correlation throughout the performance of *Bhargavi Chandrasekar - Challare Rmachandru* from 50s to 80s

As shown in Figure 4, both audio features follow a similar temporal trend with the wrist speed and the arm extension. RMS energy consistently shows higher correlations with violin-specific motion features than onset envelope. Elbow angle and arm extension exhibit the strongest correlations with RMS (732 and 547 strong windows, 45.4% and 34.0% of the performance, respectively), while wrist velocity shows a moderate correlation (253 strong windows, 15.7%). By comparison, general

motion features produce fewer strong windows for RMS (mean speed: 269, mean acceleration: 243) and onset envelope (mean speed: 118, mean acceleration: 88). For the full temporal analysis plot see Figure 14 in Appendix .1.

Dataset-wide results. Aggregating across the 15 performances, violin-specific features generate more strong correlation windows than general ones. Onset envelope shows slightly higher percentages for violin-specific features (7.14% vs 6.91%), while RMS energy shows substantially higher percentages (31.47% vs 18.30%), confirming that these features capture motion-audio relationships consistently across performances.

Interpretation. Targeted violin-specific features capture meaningful bowing-arm articulations that general motion descriptors miss. Elbow angle and arm extension show strong, consistent correlations with RMS, both within single performances and across the dataset, highlighting the robustness and relevance of instrument-specific motion descriptors.

4.2 Cross-Correlation and Lag Estimation

We computed normalized cross-correlations (Pearson r) between motion features (mean speed, mean acceleration) and audio features (onset envelope, RMS) across a lag range of $[-1, 1]$ s to detect systematic delays between gestures and sonic events. Table 1 summarizes the global and instrument-specific peak lags and corresponding correlation values. All features were resampled to 30 fps for this analysis.

After normalization, peak correlations are very small (maximum $r \approx 0.087$) and peak lags lie within ± 0.1 s. Globally, mean speed vs onset envelope peaks at $r = 0.073$ (lag -0.033 s) while correlations with RMS are weaker (e.g. mean speed vs RMS $r = 0.016$, lag -0.067 s). Per instrument, mridangam correlations are modest but consistent ($r \approx 0.065$ – 0.075 across pairs, with slight negative lags consistent with preparatory hand motion), vocals show the largest single peak (mean speed vs onset $r = 0.087$) but mixed signs with RMS, and violin correlations are generally small and more variable (peak r up to ≈ 0.069). Overall, these small correlation values

Scope	Feature pair	Lag (s)	Peak r
Global	MS-OE	-0.033	0.073
Global	MS-RMS	-0.067	0.016
Global	MA-OE	0.000	0.067
Global	MA-RMS	-0.067	0.019
Mridangam	MS-OE	-0.033	0.075
Mridangam	MS-RMS	-0.033	0.068
Mridangam	MA-OE	0.000	0.065
Mridangam	MA-RMS	-0.067	0.074
Vocal	MS-OE	-0.067	0.087
Vocal	MS-RMS	0.033	-0.056
Vocal	MA-OE	0.000	0.070
Vocal	MA-RMS	0.067	-0.049
Violin	MS-OE	-0.033	0.069
Violin	MS-RMS	0.100	0.027
Violin	MA-OE	0.000	0.066
Violin	MA-RMS	0.100	0.032

Table 1: Peak lag (s) and peak Pearson r for global and per-instrument cross-correlations. Positive lag means motion follows audio. MS = mean speed, MA = mean acceleration, OE = onset envelope, RMS = root mean square.

indicate that any systematic linear lag between motion and audio is minimal, though the computed peak lags still provide a rough estimate of potential temporal offsets. Detecting meaningful audiovisual couplings likely requires more localized or nonlinear analyses, or model-based probing, due to the limited global linear relationships and variability in motion quality and recording conditions.

Chapter 5

Model Analysis and Interpretability

5.1 Overview of Models

This chapter analyzes the behavior of three instrument-specific source separation models, each leveraging different combinations of visual and audio input. First, we examine the face + body VoViT variation developed by Rodrigues et al. [44], which uses the full audio mixture along with the facial and upper-body keypoints of the vocalist to isolate the vocal stem. Next, we analyze a vocal & violin separation model by Shankar [43], which takes the mixture and gesture keypoints from either the vocalist or violinist as input, and fuses the modalities using a self-attention-based approach, targeting the challenging task of decoupling vocal and violin sources in Carnatic music. The goal across the two cases is to study how these models behave in relation to the distinct motion and audio characteristics of each instrument, and to evaluate which input features contribute most to separation performance.

5.2 Vocalist Model

5.2.1 Model Architecture and Training

The adapted VoViT architecture for audio source separation combines audio and visual inputs, including face and body keypoints. A 4-second spectrogram is processed

through a 15-layer CNN (Spec2Vec) for audio feature extraction [48], while visual features are obtained using an 8-block Spatio-Temporal GCN [49] that captures motion from facial and body keypoints. The audio and visual features are concatenated along the channel dimension to maintain temporal alignment. These fused features are fed into a spectro-temporal Transformer, structured as an autoencoder, which predicts a complex mask. This mask is applied to the input spectrogram to produce an initial voice separation estimate. A small, audio-only UNet is then used recursively as a post-processing enhancer to reduce residual interference. The Transformer and enhancer are trained separately. The first stage of the network’s architecture is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Face + Body VoViT 1st stage architecture diagram. From Rodrigues et al. [44]

The model is trained using a mix-and-separate strategy, where clean sources are randomly mixed to create training examples. The AV Spectro-Temporal Transformer is optimized using an L2 loss between the predicted and target complex masks (after applying a tanh bounding), weighted by a gradient penalty G that emphasizes time-frequency regions with higher energy in the mixture spectrogram.

Rodrigues et al. [44] reported that the face-only model achieved the highest SDR, SIR, and SAR, followed by face + body, with body-only performing worst. This

raises the question of whether including body keypoints introduces useful cues or merely noise, motivating our interpretability analysis to examine how each visual modality contributes to voice separation.

5.2.2 Gradient-Based Interpretability

To understand how our model leverages visual input for voice separation, we apply gradient-based attribution methods. While gradients are typically used during training to update model parameters by computing $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta}$, in interpretability contexts, we instead compute the gradient of the loss \mathcal{L} with respect to the input \mathbf{x} . This allows us to estimate how sensitive the output is to changes in each input feature, essentially measuring the importance of our audiovisual features.

We apply all attribution methods over 4-second audio-visual chunks, using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between predicted and ground-truth audio as the target loss.

Vanilla Gradients

The simplest approach computes the gradient of the loss with respect to each input:

$$\text{Saliency}_i = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x_i}.$$

These raw gradients indicate which inputs would most influence the output if slightly perturbed. However, this method is often noisy due to gradient saturation or non-linearity in the model’s activations.

In practice, we found that the gradients had very low-magnitude attribution scores, and even after applying a constant scaling factor of 2^{16} (which was later used for all methods for consistency), they were hard to interpret.

Input \times Gradient

To improve interpretability, we used the Input \times Gradient method, defined as:

$$\text{Saliency}_i = x_i \cdot \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x_i}.$$

This method approximates a first-order Taylor expansion of the model’s output around a zero baseline, combining the direction of influence (the gradient) with the input’s actual magnitude. This makes attributions more meaningful than raw gradients, especially when feature scales differ, such as between subtle facial motions and broad hand gestures.

The implicit zero baseline serves as a reference point, interpreting each input’s contribution relative to its absence [50]. As with vanilla gradients, we applied a scaling factor of 2^{16} to amplify the small attribution values and aggregated saliency scores across time and space to obtain body-part-level insights.

Compared to vanilla gradients, Input \times Gradient produced clearer and more stable results, highlighting facial regions, particularly the nose and mouth. In the aggregated analysis (using the mean saliency per part), body regions showed lower importance, with the head standing out slightly among them, reinforcing the model’s reliance on facial cues. For the temporal evolution, we used the total saliency per part to reflect not only the relative importance but also the absolute contribution of each region over time. Using a zero baseline for all inputs (especially the face) remained a limitation, later addressed with a more realistic baseline in the Integrated Gradients method. Full visualizations are included in Appendix .2.

Integrated Gradients

To address limitations of Input \times Gradient, such as incomplete attributions and the sensitivity to arbitrary baselines, we implemented Integrated Gradients (IG) [51]. IG computes the average gradient along a straight-line path from a baseline input $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ to the actual input \mathbf{x} :

$$\text{IG}_i(\mathbf{x}) = (x_i - \tilde{x}_i) \int_0^1 \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}} + \alpha(\mathbf{x} - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}))}{\partial x_i} d\alpha$$

We approximate the integral using 25 steps¹, computing the gradient of the MSE loss at each interpolated input.

Baseline selection was adapted to reflect the model’s preprocessing pipeline. The audio waveform and body keypoints are both normalized and centered around zero, making a zero baseline appropriate. However, the model centers face keypoints around a dataset-wide mean during preprocessing, but unlike the other modalities, these coordinates are not normalized or scaled. This mismatch can introduce a bias in the model’s internal representations and potentially affect how attribution methods interpret the role of facial inputs. To mitigate this, we used the dataset-mean face as the baseline for facial keypoints in the Integrated Gradients method. While this choice improves alignment with the model’s actual input space, it doesn’t fully resolve the interpretability challenges introduced by the lack of normalization, particularly when comparing visual modalities². To check the impact of this baseline mismatch, we also compared attributions obtained with Integrated Gradients against those from a simpler input \times gradients method. Using the case study performance, both methods produced highly similar distributions of saliency across regions (e.g., face regions, Spearman $\rho \approx 0.86$; body regions, $\rho \approx 0.93$), suggesting that the choice of baseline does not substantially alter the relative importance patterns, even if absolute magnitudes differ.

Case study. We first illustrate the method in more detail with a single performance. For each 4-second chunk, we compute a saliency score by averaging gradient values across time and spatial dimensions. These scores are then used in two complementary analyses: a global one that averages saliency over the entire performance, and a temporal one that tracks how saliency evolves throughout the song.

The resulting saliency scores confirm earlier trends: facial regions (especially the nose, followed by the mouth) dominate the attributions. As shown in Figure 6c,

¹The authors recommend using between 20–1000 steps. We selected 25 for computational cost reasons, and verified its adequacy by comparing results with 50 steps: distributions of facial saliencies were nearly identical (symmetric Kullback-Leibler $\approx 3.9 \times 10^{-6}$, Spearman $\rho = 1.0$). <https://github.com/ankurtaly/Integrated-Gradients/blob/master/howto.md>

²This limitation should be kept in mind when interpreting results and comparing saliency across face and body regions.

Figure 6: Spatial and averaged visualization of Integrated Gradients scores for visual input modalities in the performance of *Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu* using *VoViT-fb*. Landmark radius size indicates averaged saliency score.

the more accurate baseline made the body and face scores more comparable, yet the overall distribution pattern remains. Among body parts, only the head shows a notable contribution, reinforcing the model’s reliance on facial cues for voice separation.

The facial visualization on Figure 6b reveals that the keypoints around the inner and outer lips, particularly those near the center of the mouth, exhibit the highest saliency, which aligns with the more pronounced movement of these points during mouth opening and closing. There is also a noticeable saliency concentration on

the chin, likely reflecting the role of jaw motion during singing. Another interesting find is the strong attribution present in the nose across all its keypoints, especially along the bridge. As for the body (Figure 6a, although head keypoints remain the most salient, some fingers on the right hand also show elevated saliency. This may be linked to rhythmic hand gestures or subtle movements that coincide with vocal fluctuations, suggesting the model captures not only facial articulation but also complementary body motion cues³. A more detailed view of individual keypoint contributions, grouped by body region, is provided in Appendix .3.

Temporal Integrated Gradients Evolution for Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu

Figure 7: Temporal evolution of saliency scores for major body regions throughout the performance of *Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu* using *VoViT-fb*

Moving onto the temporal analysis, Figure 7 provides a temporal breakdown of saliency scores for broader regions. While the overall importance of regions fluctuates over time, their relative rankings remain mostly stable. Facial regions consistently dominate, followed by the right hand and head. Interestingly, saliency scores across

³Although hand and finger keypoints occasionally exhibit elevated saliency, masking experiments (Table 2) show little causal effect on separation quality. These visualizations may therefore reflect incidental correlations or model noise rather than strong reliance on body cues.

all regions tend to rise and fall together, suggesting shared influence from more abstract factors such as vocal activity or model confidence, rather than isolated spikes in importance for specific regions. This interpretation is supported by the moderate positive correlations observed between saliency dynamics and separation quality (using scale-invariant signal-to-distortion ratio, SI-SDR), with values ranging from $r \approx 0.38$ for body regions to $r \approx 0.46$ for face-dominated aggregates. These results indicate that the temporal saliency modulation is not arbitrary but reflects moments where visual cues contribute more strongly to effective separation.

Figure 8: Temporal evolution of saliency scores with strong window overlay for the performance of *Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu* using *VoViT-fb*

To bridge the model-independent exploration in Chapter 4 with our current attribution analysis, we plotted the temporal evolution of aggregated face and body saliency scores, overlaying the timestamps of strong correlation windows ($|\rho| > 0.66$ over 0.5s) for both keypoint speed and acceleration (Figure 8). While acceleration events showed weak-to-moderate correlations with visual attention ($r = 0.17$ – 0.22 , with face regions most responsive), speed correlations were negligible ($r \approx 0$). Acceleration aligned with local saliency variations in some cases, but the effect size was small. Vocal-specific cues showed slightly higher associations: jaw-to-nose motion reached $r = 0.21$ – 0.24 ($p < 0.05$) with about 6 events per 4s chunk on average, and mouth area motion $r = 0.12$ – 0.22 with 5.6 events per chunk. These differences suggest that articulatory gestures may offer more consistent temporal structure than

general patterns, though the correlations remain modest overall.

Dataset-Wide Analysis. While the case study illustrates local trends, it is unclear whether these generalize. To address this, we repeated the IG analysis across the entire dataset, restricted to performances with a vocalist, violinist, and mridangam player. For each 4-second segment, we computed saliency scores for all visual keypoints and aggregated them by body region.

Rather than computing IG for every 4-second segment, we focused on two contrasting subsets:

- The top 10% of chunks with the highest number of strongly correlated frames between vocal-specific motion features and audio per performance.
- The bottom 10% of chunks with the lowest number of strong correlations.

By comparing these subsets, we test whether the model’s attributions are more meaningful when audiovisual synchrony is high.

Figure 9: Averaged IG saliency scores for different body and face parts.

Figure 9 shows the distribution of average saliency across grouped facial and body regions for these two subsets. The results reveal that the proportional distribution of keypoint saliency remains almost identical⁴ across subsets, closely resembling the pattern seen in the case study. However, the absolute scale of saliency differs

⁴The L2 distance for the normalized face and body distributions is 0.03 and 0.05 respectively

substantially: face regions exhibit saliency values an order of magnitude higher than body regions, and within each group, the top 10% subset shows attributions 2 to 3 times stronger than the bottom 10%. This indicates that while body keypoints are used minimally, the model relies heavily on facial features, especially the mouth and nose, for its predictions.

This effect was not limited to visual inputs. Audio saliency also followed the same trend, with average values of 0.0467 for the top subset and 0.0168 for the bottom subset. This suggests that in low-correlation windows the model is overall less input-dependent, potentially relying more on learned priors or exhibiting saturated behavior. Importantly, this dataset-wide result mirrors the case study (Figure 8), where peaks and valleys of face and body saliency coincided with frames of high and low audiovisual correlation. Taken together, these findings indicate that audiovisual synchrony acts primarily as a scaling factor of saliency: it modulates the overall sensitivity of the model to its inputs without altering the relative spatial distribution of attributions across keypoints.

While the face + body analysis revealed strong reliance on facial landmarks, it remained unclear whether body input dilutes or complements the facial contribution. To understand whether the body input dilutes or complements the face contribution, we extended the IG analysis to the face-only and body-only models.

Comparison with face-only and body-only models. The same integrated gradients analysis was applied to the face-only and body-only models under identical conditions to those used for the face+body model. Figure 10 shows the distributions of average saliency across facial keypoints for the face+body and face-only models. While the overall magnitude of face-only saliency is roughly half that of the face+body model, the relative distribution shifts: the mouth emerges as the most salient region, followed by the nose, whereas in the face+body model the nose exhibits the highest attribution. This suggests that when constrained to facial input alone, the model emphasizes regions most directly linked to vocalization, particularly the mouth, whereas the face+body model spreads attribution more diffusely,

including toward body keypoints that contribute relatively little (see Figure 9). This difference may help explain why the face-only model achieves stronger separation performance.

Figure 10: Averaged IG saliency across facial keypoints for face+body and face-only.

Audio saliency values further support this interpretation. While the face+body and face-only models exhibit nearly identical reliance on audio input (1.16 vs. 1.17 average saliency in the top 10%), the body-only model shows substantially higher audio saliency (1.54). This indicates that when deprived of informative facial cues, the model compensates by over-relying on the audio stream, confirming that body landmarks alone provide limited useful information for vocal separation.

For completeness, we also examined the saliency distribution of the body-only model (Figure 18 in Appendix .3). In this case, the head still emerges as the most salient region, despite the absence of facial landmarks. This suggests that even with coarse body keypoints, the model attempts to exploit head motion as a weak proxy for vocal activity, though these signals are insufficient to support effective separation.

5.2.3 Ablation Studies

To test causality rather than correlation, we performed a set of inference-time ablations that directly intervene on the visual inputs and measure the resulting change in separation quality. All ablations were executed on the vocalists on the face+body VoViT variant used in the gradient-based analysis. We report changes in SI-SDR

computed between the model’s estimate and the ground-truth target. Two complementary studies were implemented:

Temporal shuffle. The temporal shuffle script randomly permutes the time dimension of the face and body keypoint tensors within each 4-s chunk while leaving the audio unchanged. Concretely, for each sample the tensors shaped (B, T, C, K) are permuted along T , then forwarded through the frozen model to produce a separated estimate. For every (artist,song) we record the baseline SI-SDR and the shuffled SI-SDR, and compute $\Delta\text{SI-SDR} = \text{SI-SDR}_{\text{baseline}} - \text{SI-SDR}_{\text{shuffled}}$ as the per-song effect. This intervention tests whether the model requires short-term temporal alignment between gestures and sound.

Regional masking. The region masking script zeroes or replaces specific subsets of landmarks before forwarding the sample. We implemented three masks: (i) mouth, (ii) nose, and (iii) full body. Masks are filled with zeros for the body and with the respective dataset mean face keypoints for the face regions. For each masked condition we compute per-song SI-SDR and the corresponding $\Delta\text{SI-SDR}$ relative to the unmasked baseline. This directly probes which spatial regions are necessary for the model’s performance.

Results. The temporal shuffle produced essentially no effect on separation: across the dataset the average SI-SDR changed by $\Delta\text{SI-SDR} \approx -0.03$ dB (baseline ≈ 12.32 dB, shuffled ≈ 12.35 dB), indicating that destroying framewise synchrony did not meaningfully degrade performance.

By contrast, regional masking produced very large, region-specific degradations. Table 2 summarizes the face+body results

Interpretation. The tiny effect of temporal shuffling suggests the model doesn’t actually need frame-by-frame synchrony between gestures and sound, at least not at the scale we tested it⁵. In contrast, masking the mouth or nose causes a significant

⁵This intervention shuffled keypoints within 4-second chunks, which destroys fine-grained synchrony but still preserves slower-scale co-occurrence. It therefore rules out frame-level dependence but not longer-timescale audiovisual alignment.

Condition	SI-SDR (dB)	Δ SI-SDR
Baseline (unaltered visuals)	≈ 10.19	–
Mouth masked	≈ -0.67	+ 10.86
Nose masked	≈ 1.55	+ 8.64
Body masked	≈ 10.13	+ 0.06

Table 2: Regional masking results (face+body VoViT). Δ = baseline - condition; positive values indicate SI-SDR loss when the region is removed.

drop in performance, showing that facial regions around the vocal area are crucial for vocal separation. This makes sense: for singers, the mouth and nearby features carry the most direct visual evidence of when and how they are producing sound. Masking the body, on the other hand, has almost no impact, matching the attribution results where body landmarks had very low saliency. In short, the model depends heavily on which facial features are visible, but not on their precise temporal order at the scale we tested.

5.3 Vocal & Violin Model

5.3.1 Model Architecture and Training

The vocal-violin separation model builds on the VoViT framework, using a spectrogram of the audio mixture and gesture keypoints from the target source (either vocals or violin) as inputs. Audio and visual features are first extracted independently, and then fused using one of three strategies: the original face + body VoViT’s simple concatenation, FiLM-based modulation, or a Self-Attention Fusion module, our focus in this work.

In the Self-Attention Fusion Module, audio and visual features are first linearly projected into a shared latent space to ensure dimensional compatibility. These aligned embeddings are then combined using a multi-head self-attention mechanism that captures cross-modal correlations and long-range dependencies between gesture and audio. The output is further processed through a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) with a residual connection, preserving useful information from the original modality-specific features. The resulting fused representation is fed into a transformer, which

predicts a time-frequency mask. Applying this mask to the input spectrogram, followed by re-synthesis, yields the separated source. The full architecture is illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Vocal-Violin model Architecture diagram. From Shankar et al. [43]

5.3.2 Attention Analysis

To gain insight into how the model leverages visual cues during source separation, we analyze the attention weights produced by the Self-Attention Fusion module. This module integrates audio and visual representations through multi-head self-attention, allowing the model to dynamically weigh the relevance of the features of each modality when generating the fused representation used for mask prediction.

The attention weights are derived from the similarity between query and key projections of the audio and visual features. For each audio feature timestep, the weights indicate how strongly it attends to each visual timestep, forming a matrix of size (audio sequence length \times video sequence length) for each input segment.

Since attention weights are softmax-normalized, they represent relative importance. When analyzing how audio attends to visual inputs, the attention values across all visual features sum to one, showing which visual moments the model finds most relevant from the audio’s perspective. However, this structure doesn’t allow direct comparison of attention across modalities, only within each stream.

We analyzed attention weights post-training for each 4-second audio-visual segment in the dataset, using both the vocal and violin models. To get an overall picture,

we averaged attention scores across all 256 audio and 256 video features.

In both models, the original multi-head attention fusion produced an unusual pattern: video attention weights were highly concentrated on only a few dimensions, while the vast majority were pushed close to zero. This effectively suppressed most of the visual features, limiting the model’s ability to exploit gesture information (see Figure 19 on Appendix .4 for the vocal distribution, which mirrors the violin case). Further investigation revealed an architecture inconsistency in the fusion module, which limited the expressivity of the multi-head attention mechanism. Following this finding, the architecture was revised to combine FiLM with multi-head attention, rather than evaluating them separately as in the original implementation.

Figure 12: Violin Attention Weights Distribution for *VoViT-b + fusion module + FiLM*

The corrected hybrid fusion models (both vocal and violin) exhibited a much more balanced use of the video representation. As shown in Figure 12, attention weights are now distributed across a broader range of video dimensions, with some still standing out but most lying closer to an effective average delimited by the nearly uniform audio weights. Compared to the earlier sparse pattern, this indicates that the model now leverages a richer and more diverse subset of gesture cues, rather than discarding the majority of them. The vocal model exhibited a very similar distribution, provided in Figure 20 in Appendix .4.

5.3.3 FiLM Analysis

While attention analysis reveals where the model focuses within the gesture sequence, it does not capture how the visual stream modulates the audio representation. FiLM layers are well suited for this purpose, as they inject gesture cues through feature-wise scaling (γ) and shifting (β), offering a direct lens into cross-modal modulation.

Figure 13 presents the γ distributions for both models. In both cases, the distributions are strongly bimodal, with peaks around ± 5 – 7 and little mass near zero. For vocals, the distribution is sharply concentrated at the peaks, with a density reaching almost 0.5, indicating that visual cues consistently apply strong modulation to the same feature dimensions. In contrast, the violin distribution is broader, with heavier tails and peak densities below 0.2, suggesting more variability in how different features are amplified or suppressed depending on the gesture context. This implies that the violin model relies on a more distributed and flexible modulation strategy, whereas the vocal model applies more consistent, targeted modulation.

Figure 13: FiLM Gamma Distribution for Vocal & Violin models

Comparing models, the violin FiLM applies stronger modulation overall (mean $|\gamma| + |\beta| \approx 7.7$ vs. ≈ 5.4 for vocals), with a tendency to suppress more features than it boosts. This likely reflects the recording setup: since the vocal track was louder on average, the violin model needed to more aggressively suppress vocal bleed in the mixture, using gesture cues as a filter. The vocal model, by contrast, shows more

balanced modulation, with a slight bias toward feature boosting, consistent with visual cues enhancing, rather than filtering, the audio.

Quantitatively, FiLM produces large and consistent cross-modal modulation. In the face-only vocal model the per-song mean absolute scale is $|\gamma| = 4.90 \pm 0.10$ and the average total modulation $(|\gamma| + |\beta|) = 5.37 \pm 0.11$. Ablating FiLM at inference (setting $\gamma = 1, \beta = 0$) produced a substantial average performance loss ($\Delta SI - SDR = SI - SDR(original) - SI - SDR(knockout) = 12.5 \pm 4.9$, range $[-0.4, 29.2]$), showing a large, causal contribution to separation. The violin (body-only) model exhibits even stronger modulation ($|\gamma| = 6.76 \pm 0.97$, total modulation $= 7.67 \pm 1.12$) but a more variable ablation effect ($\Delta SI - SDR = -3.56 \pm 8.40$, range $[-16.5, 9.6]$), suggesting inconsistent benefit from FiLM in that case. In both models the temporal coupling between FiLM magnitude and simple audio proxies is near zero on average (vocals: onset corr ≈ -0.03 , RMS corr ≈ -0.02 ; violin: onset corr $\approx -0.02 \pm 0.14$, RMS corr $\approx -0.04 \pm 0.15$), indicating FiLM does not just track loudness or generic onsets but applies selective, visually informed modulation.

Chapter 6

Discussion and Conclusion

This chapter brings together the analyses presented in this work. We first provide a general discussion of the methodological choices made and how they shaped the investigation. We then summarize the main conclusions from the results, emphasizing on some takeaways. Finally, we outline directions for future work that could extend and deepen the findings of this thesis.

6.1 General Discussion

The aim of this thesis was to investigate how visual information contributes to music source separation, focusing on the specific yet challenging case of Carnatic concert recordings. To study this, we relied on the Saraga-AV dataset, which provides multimodal recordings of real-world performances, and examined VoViT, a state-of-the-art audiovisual source separation model.

The work proceeded in three stages. Chapter 3 was dedicated to preparing the dataset: cleaning and curating the recordings, detecting performer pose, and generating both audio and visual features. This process created a consistent multimodal representation of complex concert data and established the foundation for the analyses that followed.

In Chapter 4, we conducted an exploratory analysis of the dataset to determine

whether human-interpretable motion features (e.g., speed, acceleration) contained any relation to audio descriptors (onset envelope and RMS). The goal was not only to test for correlations but to better understand the kind of information present in the data before moving on to model-level analysis. Although overall correlations were weak, we observed that instrument-specific cues, such as mouth motion for voice and elbow angle for violin, aligned more consistently with audio activity than general motion. This finding highlighted the importance of selecting where to look for visual information depending on the instrument of interest.

Building on this context, Chapter 5 turned to the interpretability of audiovisual separation models themselves. We began by analyzing the face, body, and face+body VoViT model variants and then extended the investigation to the fusion module variants, which added multihead attention and FiLM layers to better exploit cross-modal cues. Several complementary methods were employed to test the models: gradient-based saliency analysis to reveal spatial and temporal focus, case studies of audiovisual alignment, comparisons across different input variants, ablations to assess the causal impact of visual cues, and an in-depth analysis of the fusion strategies.

Taken together, these three stages reflect a progression from data preparation, to exploratory data understanding, to model interpretability. This layered approach provided both a practical evaluation of audiovisual separation in Carnatic music and a methodological framework for disentangling how visual cues influence multimodal models.

6.2 Conclusions

The results of this work clarify how visual information contributes to music source separation in complex, real-world recordings. Dataset exploration showed that instrument-specific motion features, such as mouth movements for vocals, align more closely with audio activity than general motion, highlighting where meaningful visual cues reside.

Interpretability analyses of VoViT models revealed that facial landmarks dominate visual contributions for vocal separation, while body motion is largely peripheral. Ablations confirmed the causal relevance of these visual features. For higher-performing vocal and violin models, feature fusion through multihead attention and FiLM layers enabled selective cross-modal modulation, showing that the models can amplify or suppress audio features based on visual context.

Overall, visual cues can meaningfully support source separation, but their impact is instrument- and region-specific. The findings underline the importance of targeted visual feature selection and carefully designed fusion mechanisms in multimodal music separation systems.

6.3 Future Work

The insights and limitations of this thesis open up several promising paths for future research. First, the analytical framework developed here could be extended to other musical traditions and instruments, such as hindustani music, to evaluate whether similar visual dominance patterns and cross-modal modulation principles hold. Insights from our interpretability analyses suggest that models could be made more efficient by prioritizing the most informative visual features, such as facial landmarks, and by designing FiLM-like modulatory mechanisms tailored to specific separation tasks. Another promising direction is connecting keypoint-based analyses with pixel-level saliency methods, which could reveal whether models trained on raw video naturally attend to the same informative regions. Finally, the understanding of audiovisual relationships gained here could inform generative and cross-modal synthesis, enabling models to predict or synthesize performer gestures from audio, or vice versa, in a musically meaningful way.

In summary, this thesis has provided an integrated investigation into how visual information interacts with audio in music source separation, focusing on the challenging case of Carnatic performance. By combining dataset-driven analysis, cross-domain evaluation, and interpretability methods, it has offered a clearer picture of

the selective but meaningful role of visual cues. While the findings are necessarily bounded by data and model constraints, they demonstrate the value of a multi-modal perspective and lay the groundwork for more robust and culturally inclusive approaches to audiovisual music processing.

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.1 Temporal Correlation Analysis Plots

Figure 14: Temporal evolution of violin motion features vs audio features correlation throughout the performance of *Bhargavi Chandrasekar - Challare Rmachandru*

.2 Input \times Gradient Plots

Aggregated Saliency Distribution for Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu

Figure 15: Aggregated Input \times Gradient saliency scores for different body and face parts in the performance of *Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu* using *VoViT-fb*

Temporal Saliency Evolution for Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu

Figure 16: Temporal evolution of saliency scores for major body regions throughout the performance of *Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu* using *VoViT-fb*

.3 Integrated Gradient Plots

Saliency Distribution for Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu

Figure 17: Integrated Gradients saliency scores for all body and face keypoints over the performance of *Abhiram Bode - Entha Bhagyamu* using *VoViT-fb*

Figure 18: Averaged IG saliency across body keypoints for face+body and body-only.

.4 Attention Analysis Plots

Figure 19: Vocal Attention Weights Distribution for $VoViT-f + fusion\ module$

Figure 20: Vocal Attention Weights Distribution for $VoViT-f + fusion\ module + film$